

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025–2026

Pursina, Mary Grace G.¹, Pampilo, John Benedict G.², & Simon, Russel Kean N.³

¹Department of Teacher Education, Cavite State University CCAT Campus, Rosario, Cavite, Philippines

*Correspondence: ¹marygrace.pursina@cvsu.edu.ph, ²johnbenedict.pampilo@cvsu.edu.ph, ³russelkean.simon@cvsu.edu.ph

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to develop and evaluate a HOTS-based knowledge test for BSIT major in Electronics Technology students enrolled in course ENSC 33A. In addition, the study aimed to evaluate students' performance in terms of environmental concepts, test types, and clarity of instructions and determine its effectiveness as a basis for an academic repository test. To achieve these objectives, the researchers designed a 45-items knowledge test aligned with Bloom's Taxonomy and was validated by the assistance of subject experts. The test was administered to a sample of 30 students using a research and development approach supported by descriptive statistics and qualitative notes. Primary data were collected through the administration of the test and post-assessment survey. The findings revealed that students generally demonstrated a basic understanding of environmental concepts, with adjusted mean scores between 4.17 and 4.44. Performance was strongest in sustainable practices, where passing students achieved a mean of 4.769 in diagram-based assessments. While difficulties were observed in applying and evaluating concepts related to energy conservation and waste management, where failing students recorded their lowest mean of 1.647 in matching-type tests, and in waste management multiple-choice items, which yielded a low average mean of 1.941.

Keywords: *Higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), Knowledge test, Environmental science, BSIT students, Environmental concepts, Test types, Instructions, Cavite State University*

1. Introduction

Norms in Environmental Science prevails as it is quoted as a subject grounded merely in common sense or moral responsibility. This perception limits students' understanding of its broader significance that seeks to address relevant environmental issues by equipping learners with the ability to reason critically, solve complex environmental issues, and make informed decisions (Aruta, 2022; Allawan, 2023). In the context of electronics technology students, this gap becomes more urgent, as the field involves waste management, energy consumption, and actions to support sustainability.

This concern is supported by several studies which show how low environmental awareness and inconsistent practices should be addressed immediately, especially in the context of environmental science education because it contributes to rising environmental

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025–2026

issues present in the country (Aruta & Ballada, 2022; Corpuz, 2023; Galorio & Naling, 2024; Simpao & Yabut, 2022). Therefore, addressing the lack of assessment tools that accurately measure students' higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) in Environmental Science is necessary for resolving these issues.

This is evident as previous studies have highlighted the essential role of environmental education in building a globally aware citizenry capable of addressing present and future environmental challenges (Galorio & Naling, 2024). Research has also emphasized the importance of using valid assessment tools to measure not only factual knowledge but also the application of higher-order reasoning, including rational, introspective, metacognitive, and creative thinking (Yildirim et al., 2024; Loyens et al., 2023). Furthermore, assessments promoting HOTS enhance learners' critical thinking, judgment, and ability to solve problems (Mardiana, 2023; Seagan et al., 2025).

To address this gap, the present study proposed the development of a HOTS-based knowledge test specifically designed for the Environmental Science course with the code of ENSC 33A in Cavite State University - CCAT Campus. The assessment aimed to measure the cognitive depth and ability of students to analyze, evaluate, and apply environmental concepts within the context of electronics technology. By integrating HOTS based on Bloom's taxonomy, the creation of knowledge test offers a structured and reliable approach to students' true competencies in Environmental Science. Furthermore, this study contributes to more equitable and evidence-based education decisions and will enable the institution to accurately assess learning outcomes and improve instructions.

2. Methodology

This study utilized Research and Development design. It aims to develop a HOTS-based knowledge test for BSIT Major in Electronics Technology students of Cavite State University–CCAT Campus. The knowledge test included three (3) environmental science topics mainly: Waste Management, Energy conservation, and sustainable practices, with three (3) different test types: Multiple Choice Questions, Matching-Type and Categorization Tests, and Image/Diagram-Based Questions followed by Feedback Survey Questionnaire.

The results obtained from the knowledge test and feedback survey questionnaire were analyzed using Table of Specification (TOS) to address objective one (1). Subsequently, descriptive statistics and item-analysis for difficulty and discrimination was utilized for objective two (2). Similarly, objective three (3) was addressed through descriptive statistics. To conclude, a thematic analysis or qualitative notes was used for objective four (4).

The knowledge test was administered to BSIT Major in Electronics Technology students enrolled in ENSC 33A during the Academic Year 2025–2026 at Cavite State University – CCAT Campus. Purposive sampling was employed to select participants who were directly involved in the course, ensuring that the data gathered were relevant to the study's objectives. In addition, demographic information, such as age, gender, and academic standing, was collected to provide context for the analysis of students' performance.

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025–2026

The results were organized according to environmental concepts, test types, clarity of instructions, and levels of cognitive demand. The data were then analyzed through descriptive statistics using JASP statistical software. The post-assessment survey was further evaluated through thematic analysis to identify strengths and weaknesses of student’s performance. These data approaches provided comprehensive results of how students engaged with higher-order thinking tasks across different assessments.

For ethical considerations, the respondents were informed about the purpose, nature, scope, and procedures of the study. Informed consent is obtained to ensure that participation is entirely voluntary. The study adheres to established principles of research integrity and morally upright, ensuring that all processes are conducted honestly, responsibly, and transparently. Throughout the administering of knowledge tests, the researchers prioritized the dignity, rights, and well-being of all participants.

Overall, the methodology provided a systematic and reliable framework for evaluating the 45-item HOTS-based environmental science knowledge test administered to BSIT Electronics Technology students. The research and development design enabled researchers to use appropriate data analysis techniques and adhere to ethical standards. The findings served as a basis for repository test development and instructional improvement in other areas of science.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Level of Cognitive Depth

Table 1. Student’s Score in Developed HOTS-based Knowledge Test

	No.													
	29	36	34	24	27	33	35	28	32	37	23	22	18	19
Valid	3	3	3	2	5	2	2	3	2	1	1	1	1	1
Mis.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	16.67	10.00	9.67	11.00	23.80	14.50	9.00	15.00	17.00	15.00	16.00	17.00	19.00	20.00
SD	13.58	9.84	5.89	9.89	10.57	12.02	1.41	9.21	6.36					
Min	1.000	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	8.00	9.00	13.00	15.00	16.00	17.00	19.00	20.00
Max	25.00	21.00	14.00	18.00	30.00	23.00	10.00	26.00	22.00	15.00	16.00	17.00	19.00	20.00

The table shows that top-performing students, such as Student 27 with a mean of 23.80, and maximum score of 30.00, demonstrate a higher capacity for higher-order thinking, suggesting an ability to critique environmental scenarios or justify ecological solutions.

In contrast, students like No. 35 and No. 36 with a mean of 9.00 and maximum score of 10.00, respectively score significantly lower, indicating a struggle to transition from basic comprehension to the analytical requirements of the test. The high standard deviation of 13.58 observed in students like No. 29 highlights that the depth of thinking appears to be inconsistent or topic dependent.

3.2 Cognitive Depth Performance in Environmental Concepts

Table 2. Students' Remarks in Waste Management

	Test 1		Test 2		Test 3	
	0	1	0	1	0	1
Valid	17	13	17	13	17	13
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	1.941	2.846	4.059	4.077	4.059	4.077
Std. Deviation	0.899	0.555	0.899	0.760	0.899	0.760
Minimum	0.000	2.000	2.000	3.000	2.000	3.000
Maximum	3.000	4.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000

The table indicates that students' cognitive depth increases as they move from verbal to visual assessments. The multiple choice (Test 1) section yielded the lowest results, with failing students with an average mean of 1.941 and passing students with mean 2.846, suggesting that identifying analytical concepts in a multiple-choice format is a challenge.

However, the performance improved significantly in the matching type (Test 2) and diagram-based (Test 3) sections. This upward trend suggests that students are better at evaluating waste management systems when they can visualize the relationships between components.

Notably, passing students in Test 1 showed a very low standard deviation of 0.555, indicating a highly consistent baseline for those who successfully navigate the analysis level of this topic.

Table 3. Students' Remarks in Energy Conservation

	Test 1		Test 2		Test 3	
	0	1	0	1	0	1
Valid	17	13	17	13	17	13
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.118	3.846	1.647	4.308	2.647	3.385
Std. Deviation	1.219	1.214	1.498	1.032	0.862	0.961
Minimum	1.000	2.000	0.000	2.000	1.000	2.000
Maximum	5.000	5.000	4.000	5.000	4.000	5.000

The table highlights a critical cognitive gap specifically within the matching type (Test 2) format. In this section, failing students achieved their lowest mean of 1.647, while passing students maintained a high mean of 4.308. This suggests that the evaluation required to correctly match energy-saving strategies with its specific ecological impacts is a primary factor that separates successful students from failing students.

While students in both groups showed moderate success in the multiple choice (Test 1) and diagram-based (Test 3) sections, the high standard deviation of 1.498 among

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025–2026

failing students points to a lack of conceptual stability when asked to judge and connect different energy conservation models.

Table 4. Students' Remarks in Sustainable Practices

	Test 1		Test 2		Test 3	
	0	1	0	1	0	1
Valid	17	13	17	13	17	13
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	1.765	2.615	2.824	4.231	3.706	4.769
Std. Deviation	0.970	1.044	2.038	1.166	1.532	0.439
Minimum	0.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.000	4.000
Maximum	4.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000

The table shows a steady upward trend in cognitive depth as students move through the test formats. The multiple choice (Test 1) section highlights the lowest scores, indicating that analyzing sustainability with various choices were challenging. However, the diagram-based (Test 3) assessment produced the highest level of cognitive depth recorded across all topics, with passing students reaching a mean of 4.769 and a minimum score of 4.000.

This result suggests that the highest level of evaluation is assessing the long-term possibility of sustainable practices. Hence, it is most effectively demonstrated when students are required to interpret or complete complex environmental diagrams, which likely require a deeper comprehension of information than standard multiple-choice questions.

3.3 Evaluation of Student Performance

The evaluation of student's strengths and weaknesses was analyzed through descriptive statistics using the total score of students for each environmental concept: waste management, energy conservation, and sustainable practices; and the total score of the student's survey using a 5-point Likert scale. Hence, the mean for each table was adjusted to a 5-point scale.

Table 5. Specific Environmental Concepts

	Topic 1		Topic 2		Topic 3	
	0	1	0	1	0	1
Valid	17	13	17	13	17	13
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	8.882	8.846	8.353	8.846	8.882	8.615
Std. Deviation	1.495	1.214	1.693	1.214	1.728	1.193
Minimum	4.000	7.000	3.000	6.000	3.000	6.000
Maximum	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00

Students perceive the conceptual understanding of environmental science as a significant strength, with mean scores for all three topics: Waste Management, Energy Conservation, and Sustainable Practices, consistently falling between adjusted mean of 4.17 and 4.44.

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025–2026

While students who failed the knowledge test reported very similar levels of conceptual confidence as those who passed, particularly in waste management and sustainable practices where adjusted means were approximately 4.44 and 4.31 respectively.

A minor relative weakness is noted in energy conservation for failing students, who reported their lowest conceptual mean of 4.1, reflecting the lower performance trends seen in the actual knowledge test for that topic.

Table 6. Test Types

	Multiple Choice		Matching Type		Diagram-Based	
	0	1	0	1	0	1
Valid	17	13	17	13	17	13
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	12.47	12.00	12.82	12.54	12.41	12.85
Std. Deviation	2.809	2.000	3.167	1.713	2.501	1.573
Minimum	4.000	9.000	3.000	10.00	5.000	11.00
Maximum	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00

In terms of test types, the diagram-based test highlights strength for higher-performing students, who reported a high mean preference of 4.28 with the lowest standard deviation of 1.573, indicating a consistent and cohesive visual higher-order thinking.

The multiple choice and matching type assessment represent a weakness in terms of consistency for students who failed the test, as evidenced by higher standard deviations of 2.809 and 3.167 respectively. These high variability values suggest that lower-performing students find it unpredictable resulting in low demonstration of cognitive depth.

Furthermore, while failing students perceived matching type as a strength with an adjusted mean of 4.27, the actual performance in the knowledge test was often lower in this format, highlighting a disconnection between student preference and its ability to execute evaluation tasks.

Table 7. Instructions

	Diagram-Based		Matching Type		Multiple Choice	
	0	1	0	1	0	1
Valid	17	13	17	13	17	13
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	4.235	4.154	4.294	4.385	4.353	4.308
SD	0.970	0.801	1.047	0.768	1.057	0.630
Minimum	1.000	3.000	1.000	3.000	1.000	3.000
Maximum	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000

The clarity of instructions is a highlighted strength of the developed instrument, as all adjusted mean scores across every test type exceeded 4.1. Students who passed the test found the instructions for matching type with adjusted mean of 4.385 and multiple choice with mean of 4.308 to be particularly clear, ensuring that the student's performance was likely a true reflection of cognitive depth rather than complicated process.

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University-CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025-2026

A very slight relative weakness or area for refinement is the diagram-based instructions, which received the lowest mean from the "passed" group at mean of 4.154. While still a high score, this indicates that as students move toward the more complex level of HOTS which are evaluation and analysis required by diagrams, the instructions must be clear and direct to support better performance.

3.4 Qualitative Notes

Strong Basic Understanding but Varying Higher-Order Performance

The thematic analysis for qualitative addressed the objective four (4) of the study. It examined the strengths and weaknesses shown by student's performance on the developed HOTS-based Environmental Science knowledge test. The analysis is organized according to (a) specific environmental concepts, (b) test types, and (c) clarity and effectiveness of instructions.

Results show that students generally have a good basic understanding of key environmental concepts, including Waste Management, Energy Conservation, and Sustainable Practices. Survey results indicate that both passing and failing students rated their conceptual understanding highly. This suggests that most students are familiar with the content at a foundational level.

A clear strength is seen in Sustainable Practices, where students especially those who passed performed well in tasks that required analysis and evaluation. When students were asked to interpret diagrams or assess long-term environmental effects, they demonstrated stronger higher-order thinking skills.

Difficulty Applying Concepts in Energy Conservation

Despite high self-reported confidence, Energy Conservation emerged as a weaker area in actual test performance. Students, particularly those who failed, struggled with tasks that required them to match conservation strategies with their environmental impacts. This indicates that while students may understand concepts in theory, they find it challenging to apply and evaluate them in more complex situations.

Diagram-Based Tests Support Higher-Order Thinking

Diagram-based test items were a major strength of the assessment. Students who passed the test performed best in this format across all topics. Diagrams helped students visualize relationships and systems, making it easier for them to analyze information and evaluate environmental solutions. The consistent performance among high-scoring students suggests that visual formats effectively support higher-order thinking.

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University-CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025-2026

Text-Based Formats Pose Greater Challenges

Multiple-choice and matching-type tests showed more weaknesses, especially among lower-performing students. Multiple-choice items that relied heavily on text resulted in lower scores, suggesting difficulty in analyzing information without visual support. Matching-type items showed wide differences in performance, particularly in Energy Conservation, indicating that these tasks may require cognitive skills that some students have not yet fully developed.

Clear Instructions as a Strength of the Test

One strong aspect of the developed test is the clarity of its instructions. Students from both passing and failing groups rated the instructions highly across all test types. This suggests that students generally understood what was required of them, and their performance reflects their level of thinking rather than confusion about procedures.

Slight Need for Improvement in Diagram-Based Instructions

Although still rated positively, instructions for diagram-based items received slightly lower ratings compared to other formats. This suggests that as tasks become more complex, students may benefit from clearer or more detailed instructions to better guide their responses.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

The development of the 45-item HOTS-based knowledge test in Environmental Science (ENSC 33A) successfully established a structured tool for measuring cognitive depth among BSIT Electronics Technology students at Cavite State University-CCAT Campus. The findings reveal that the instrument effectively measures student's higher order thinking skills (HOTS), specifically their ability to analyze, evaluate, and apply specific environmental concepts in real-world settings.

In contrast, it was also revealed that while students generally possess a solid foundational knowledge of environmental concepts, particularly in waste management and sustainable practices, students experienced a significant "cognitive gap." Students struggled to apply and evaluate concepts mainly in energy conservation topic. Despite showing a high conceptual confidence level in this area with a mean of 4.10, failing students recorded their lowest actual performance in this topic, specifically with a mean score of 1.647 in the matching-type test. This discrepancy suggests a misalignment between the perceived understanding and performance of students highlighting the importance of assessment tools that go beyond recalling and effectively measure cognitive depth.

Among the test formats, diagram-based items proved to be the most effective in eliciting higher-order thinking, enabling students to visualize systems and relationships within environmental contexts. In contrast, multiple-choice and matching-type items posed

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025–2026

greater challenges, particularly for lower-performing students, indicating variability in students' analytical and evaluative abilities. Additionally, the instructions across all test types received high ratings, ensuring that performance reflected cognitive skills rather than procedural confusion, while suggesting the need for minor refinement for more complex items.

Overall, the developed 45-Item HOTS-based knowledge test demonstrates validity and instructional value and can serve as a reliable basis for an academic repository test in Environmental Science and related disciplines.

To enhance the development of a repository test based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed. For instructors and curriculum designers, active integration of diagram-based and context-driven assessments to better support the development of higher-order thinking skills and bridge the gap between theory and practice in environmental science.

Academic departments may enhance the knowledge test by balancing visual and text-based items with clearer instructions to ensure the instrument remains cognitively rigorous while accommodating diverse learning styles.

Finally, future researchers may conduct a similar study with a larger, more diverse sample size including other academic programs to further validate the reliability of the instrument and explore the effectiveness of technology-assisted assessments in measuring students' environmental reasoning skills.

Conflict of Interest Statement. *The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper. The research was conducted independently and did not receive any funding or support that could influence the outcomes or interpretations presented herein.*

5. References

- Amin, M. S. (2025). Development and feasibility of environmental knowledge test instruments with low carbon education content for prospective science teachers. *jurnal.uin-antasari.ac.id*. <https://doi.org/10.18592/tarbiyah.v14i1.15823>
- Ann, H., Mahinay, C., Shenny, M., Marapao, A., Hua, J., Jempero, B., Allawan, J. G., & Allawan, L. (2023). Environmental literacy levels and environmental pollution among senior high school students. *Journal of Environmental Impact and Management Policy*, 03, 17–25. <https://doi.org/10.55529/jeimp.36.17.25>
- Aruta, J. J. B. R. (2022). Science literacy promotes energy conservation behaviors in Filipino youth via climate change knowledge efficacy: Evidence from PISA 2018. *Australian Journal of Environmental Education*, 39(1), 55–66. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aee.2022.10>
- Aruta, J. J. B. R., Ballada, C. J. A. (2022). The impact of nature relatedness on environmental attitudes weakens among materialistic individuals: Evidence from the Philippines. *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*.

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025–2026

- Bacolod, D. (2021). Teaching the environmental science education in the 21st century. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 9, 1908–1917. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/v9i10.e103>
- Barrun, J., Cajurao, E. (2025). Development and validation of contextualized lessons in Science, Technology, and Society (STS): Impacts on students' conceptual understanding, science process skills, and attitudes toward science. www.pegegog.net. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pegegog.15.02.04>
- Castilla, N. D. G., Abucay, N. G. M. J., Aguilar, N. L. J. H., Avila, N. K. L. G., & Momo, N. R. A. (2024). Waste disposal knowledge, attitude, and practices of Barangay Poblacion, Compostela, Cebu, Philippines. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 12(1), 2146–2157. <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijstra.2024.12.1.0987>
- Corpuz, A. M. (2023). Knowledge and adaptation practices: Baseline data for the development of climate change engagement model. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Applied Business and Education Research*, 4(6), 1920–1931. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.04.06.18>
- Cueno, P. L., Mistades, V. M. (2024). Use of contextualized activity sheets in improving students' knowledge on climate change. *Asian Conference on Education Official Conference Proceedings/ACE*, 401–405. <https://doi.org/10.22492/issn.2186-5892.2024.35>
- Dulama, E., Ilovan, O.-R. (2025). Study on completion test items used in science knowledge assessment, 1, 50–64.
- Galorio, I. J. N., Naling, C. S. (2024). Awareness and practices of senior high school students and teachers on environmental education: Basis for instructional materials development. *Asian Journal of Environment & Ecology*, 23(4), 16–39. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajee/2024/v23i4537>
- Gazzaz, N. M., Aldeseet, B. A. (2021). Assessment of the level of knowledge of climate change of undergraduate science and agriculture students. *World Journal of Education*, 11(5), 41. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wje.v11n5p41>
- Gradini, E., Khairunnisak, C., & Noviani, J. (2022). Development of higher-order thinking skill (HOTS) test on mathematics in secondary school. *AKSIOMA Jurnal Program Studi Pendidikan Matematika*, 11(1), 319. <https://doi.org/10.24127/ajpm.v11i1.4649>
- Jailani, J., Sugiman, S., & Apino, E. (2017). Implementing the problem-based learning in order to improve the students' HOTS and characters. *Jurnal Riset Pendidikan Matematika*, 4(2), 247. <https://doi.org/10.21831/jrpm.v4i2.17674>
- Kusumaningtyas, D. A., Manyunuh, M., Kurniasari, E., Awal, A. N., Rahmaniati, R., & Febriyanti, A. (2024). Enhancing learning outcomes: A study on the development of higher order thinking skills-based evaluation instruments for work and energy in high school physics. *Indonesian Journal on Learning and Advanced Education (IJOLAE)*, 14–31. <https://doi.org/10.23917/ijolae.v6i1.23125>

Nurturing HOTS for Nature: Development of a HOTS-Based Knowledge Test in ENSC 33A for BSIT Electronics Technology Students at Cavite State University–CCAT Campus A.Y. 2025–2026

- Player, L., Hanel, P. H., Whitmarsh, L., & Shah, P. (2023). The 19-item Environmental Knowledge Test (EKT-19): A short, psychometrically robust measure of environmental knowledge. *Heliyon*, 9(8), e17862. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17862>
- Seagan, G. M., Encarnacion, A., Aragon, A., Acampado, C., & Villanueva, R. R. (2025). The development of BSES 26 knowledge test for BSE 201 science students of Cavite State University – CCAT Campus A.Y. 2024–2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14713887>
- Sidiq, Y., Ishartono, N., Dessty, A., Prayitno, H. J., Anif, S., & Hidayat, M. L. (2021). Improving elementary school students' critical thinking skill in science through HOTS-based science questions: A quasi-experimental study. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 10(3), 378–386. <https://doi.org/10.15294/jpii.v10i3.30891>
- Simpao, A. C., Yabut, H. (2022). Conservation behavior among students in a university in Metro Manila: The moderating role of attitudes on the impact of environmental knowledge. *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, 22, 95–108. <https://doi.org/10.59588/2350-8329.1466>
- Sunardi, N. H. B. H. S. R. S. (2023). Higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) in environmental learning at Indonesian high school. *Tuijin Jishu/Journal of Propulsion Technology*, 44(3), 3440–3453. <https://doi.org/10.52783/tjpt.v44.i3.2054>
- U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. (2025, August 4). What is environmental education? <https://www.epa.gov/education/what-environmental-education>
- Valid and reliable assessments. CSAI Update. (n.d.). <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED588476>
- Yildirim, P., Keçeci, G., & ZengiN, F. K. (2024). Development of a knowledge test about scientists for secondary school students. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 11(1), 126–147. <https://doi.org/10.21449/ijate.1351510>